

Hybrid Performance Prediction Models for Fully-Connected Neural Networks on MPSoC

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Abstract—Predicting the performance of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) on embedded multi-core platforms is tedious. Concurrent accesses to shared resources are hard to model due to congestion effects on the shared communication medium, which affect the performance of the application. In this paper we present a hybrid modeling environment to enable fast yet accurate timing prediction for fully-connected ANNs deployed on multi-core platforms. The modeling flow is based on the integration of an analytical computation time model with a communication time model which are both calibrated through measurement inside a system level simulation using SystemC. The proposed flow enables the prediction of the end-to-end latency for different mappings of several fully-connected ANNs with an average of more than 99% accuracy.

Keywords — Model of Performance, Multi Processor, SystemC simulation, Artificial Neural Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

The demand for smart multi-core embedded systems used to execute Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) has increased exponentially in the last few years. Deploying ANNs on such devices is tough as ANNs are computation-intensive application with high memory needs whereas embedded platforms lack of computational resources and memory, and often bear strong timing and energy constraints. To ease the development effort and allow the optimization of the implemented solutions, early performance evaluation for ANNs on MPSoC is needed.

Several approaches have been carried out to tackle the challenge of performance evaluation for ANNs on embedded platforms. Some approaches focus on evaluation through implementation and testing [1] [2]. This evaluation technique doesn't enable a comprehensive exploration of the design space due to the long development time needed to systematically deploy the ANN. Other works focus on the building of analytical models [3] [4], however such models lack of accuracy when targeting a large scale of architectures composed of multiple processing elements. On these architectures concurrent accesses on shared elements can cause congestions, which surge execution time and are hard to model.

To tackle this challenge we present in this paper an innovative modeling environment used for fast-yet-accurate performance prediction for fully-connected ANNs, also called Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs), deployed on MPSoC. This modeling environment combines simulation, analytical models and partial characterization through measurements. We

demonstrate the effectiveness of our flow by predicting the performance of several partitionings and mappings of two MLPs on architectures containing up to 7 cores with an average accuracy of more than 99%.

II. MODELING AND SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

A schematic of the proposed environment is given in Fig. 1. This figure highlights the steps to build performance models used to predict execution time of MLPs deployed on multi-core platforms. The first activity captured in orange focuses on the description of the MLP in the Synchronous Data Flow (SDF) Model of Computation (MoC) (1.) and its mapping on the targeted platform (2.). SDF offers a strict separation of computation and communications (read, write) of actors. Computation and communication separation eases the performance prediction process by allowing building separated computation time and communication time models. To apply the SDF MoC to fully-connected ANNs, we define a cluster as a given set of neurons from the same layer, which execution is modeled as an actor. The number of actors (i.e. the number of clusters) by layer is established based on the desired granularity. Two examples of SDF graph of different complexity are given in Step 1. of Fig. 1. The next step aims at mapping the ANN on the targeted architecture. The considered architecture is composed of a set of tiles. A tile is one processing element with its private memory. Actors of the SDF graph are mapped on the tiles and communication channels are mapped on the shared memory. An example of mapping is depicted in Step 2. of Fig. 1.

The next activity highlighted in purple focuses on the building of a simulable model (5.) using the developed computation and communication time models (3. and 4.). The computation time model is an hybrid analytical model calibrated by measurements. It can predict accurately performance for any considered level of granularity used to describe ANN applications. The communication time model is a message level model that was introduced in previous work [5]. Both the computation time model and the communication time model are integrated in a high level simulation of the architecture executing the application. This allows to perform a timing analysis of the ANN executed on the targeted platform.

The third activity highlighted in green focuses on the measurement of delays on a real platform (6.) in order to

Fig. 1: Schematic of the proposed environment. This flow aims at enabling performance prediction for fully-connected ANNs on multi-core platforms. The processes marked with the * symbol are novel features to our flow.

calibrate the timing models and compare the simulation results with real execution times. The final activity highlighted in yellow focus on the validation of the proposed models by comparing the predictions to the measured execution times (7.) and the exploration of several grains and mappings to optimize latency using the proposed models (8.).

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

To characterize our models of performance and to validate their predictions we implemented a hardware platform that followed the hypothesis of the proposed model of architecture. We implemented this platform on both a Xilinx Ultrascale MPSoC+ and a Xilinx Zynq7000 FPGAs. A tile is composed of a MicroBlaze processor and a local memory implemented as BRAM. The platform is composed of 7 tiles and a shared memory connected via an AXI shared interconnect. It implements a time measurement infrastructure which allows measuring the delays needed for the whole SDF graph execution or actor execution. The computation and communication time models have been calibrated with elementary delays measured using this infrastructure. In this work, the ANNs are implemented using the lightweight open source library LibFANN [6] which enables the training and execution of MLPs in C programming language. To verify and validate our modeling approach, we considered two MLPs with different topologies. Both applications were developed and trained to perform digit recognition using the MNIST data set.

In order to test the accuracy of the proposed models for several levels of complexity of SDF graphs, a set of SDF graphs with different grains were used for both applications. Several mappings were also considered for each of these SDF graphs, which uses up to 7 tiles and rely both on parallel and pipeline execution. The predicted end-to-end latencies by the proposed simulative model are compared with the end-to-end latencies measured on the real platform for several scenarios. We also compared the predictions of the computation time model used alone against the real durations. The predictions of the computation time model only are too optimistic and bear 10.5% error on average for the presented scenarios. In order to predict the execution time of ANNs on multi-core platforms, a computation time model alone is not sufficient and the modeling of communications is necessary. The system

level simulative model averages more than 99% accuracy for all the considered scenarios. The highest prediction error is 2.89% for a complex 7-tiles scenario that benefits both from parallel and pipeline execution. In this scenario the average communication time of tiles counts for 89% of the execution time. For all the other scenarios, the error of the simulative model is less than 1%. This validates the proposed model for the prediction of execution time of MLPs on multi-core platforms. Once validated, the modeling approach can be used to explore other partitionings and mappings and find optimized solutions.

IV. CONCLUSION

Our hybrid modeling environment enables accurate performance prediction for MLPs on MPSoC architectures containing up to 7 tiles. It achieves overall 99% accuracy for estimating the end-to-end latency for two MLPs trained using the MNIST data-set. In future work, we will extend the presented modeling environment to enable the exploration of the design space for several classes of ANNs under both timing and energy constraints. We will propose a power and energy modeling flow that will be validated by comparing with real consumption measured on the execution platform, as well as evaluating the effect of power management methods on the execution time and energy consumption of ANNs.

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